

INFLUENCE OF BREAKFAST SKIPPING ON TEACHING-LEARNING PROCESS OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ONDO WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of breakfast skipping on teaching and learning process of senior secondary school (SSS) students in Ondo West Local Government Area (OWLGA) of Ondo State. It employed descriptive survey research design. Thirteen students from SS1 and SS2 were randomly selected from the ten schools selected for the study in the Local Government Area to make a total of two hundred and sixty (260) SSS students. Data were analysed using frequency counts and mean (\bar{X}). Factors responsible for breakfast skipping of the students in OWLGA were: not having enough time to eat in the morning, not feeling hungry in the morning, a feeling of being weak and sleepy after eating breakfast among others. Skipping breakfast was observed to reduce students' concentration during classroom instruction, lead to confusion, reduce learning ability reduce mental fitness, and makes students uncomfortable for learning. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that; there should be abundant provision for the feeding needs of wards by their parents students should be encouraged to take their breakfast before going to school and develop habit of waking up early in the morning to prepare breakfast.

Key words: *Students, Breakfast, Breakfast Skipping, Learning, Teaching,*

Introduction

Breakfast is the first meal taken after rising from bed, early in the morning before undertaking the day's work. The word breakfast literal refers to breaking the fasting period of the prior night. It has its origin in the Christian custom of fasting between supper meals of one night after receiving Holy Communion the following morning. Breakfast foods vary widely from place to place but often include; carbohydrates, such as grains or cereals, fruits, vegetables, protein foods such as, egg, meat

fish and beverages such as, tea, coffee, milk or fruit juice, vegetable and baked beans. Researches have shown that people, who skip breakfast are likely to have problems of concentration, metabolism, and cardiac health (Phillips, 2005; Widenhorn-Müller, Hille, Klenk and Weiland, 2008; Deshmukh-Taskar, Nicklas, O'Neil, Keast, Radcliffe, and Cho, 2010; Szajewska and Ruszczyński, 2010; Adolphus, Lawton and Dye, 2013). Apart from providing energy, breakfast foods are good sources of important nutrients such as, calcium, iron, and B-vitamins as well as, protein and fibers required by the body (Frank, 2009). Previous research has shown that, if these essential nutrients are missed during breakfast, they are less likely to be compensated for later in the day. Breakfast is essential for weight control and for brain development (Berkey, Rockett, Gillman, Field and Colditz, 2003)

The Adolescent need breakfast each day to perform their best. The growing body cells and developing brain need regular refueling which is often from food. When adolescents skip breakfast they do not get what they need to be at their best. Eating a wholesome nutritious morning meal will probably save time in the long-run by recharging the brain and body which consequently makes the individual to be more efficient in just about everything he or she does. Students who skip breakfast are tardy (sluggish) and absent from school more often than those who eat breakfast on a regular basis (Wesnes, Pincock and Scholey, 2012). Eating of breakfast also help to improve teaching-learning and allow students to do better in tests and examinations (Kleinman, Hall, Green, Korzec-Ramirez, Patton and Pagano, 2002).

Nutrients are important for optimal brain development and function. Although, intake of nutrients throughout one's life-time is important. Certain nutrients have more profound effects on cognitive development than others (Hoyland, Dye and Lawton, 2009). Studies also revealed that, breakfast skipping between certain ages such as, 10-11 years has notable impact on a child's learning ability or ability to succeed in school especially, when it comes to a short-term memory challenge need, the individual needs a lot of fuel for the growing cells to thrive. So, if anyone skips breakfast, the cells become starve, the brain cannot learn and muscles cannot grow (Deshmukh-Taskar, Nicklas, O'Neil, Keast, Radcliffe, and Cho, 2010).

Breakfast helps to improve mental performance and concentration, during morning activities. Those taking breakfast often perform better in their school work and show extra energy in sporting and other physical activities (Staub, 2000; Phillips, 2005; Widenhorn-Müller, Hille, Klenk and Weiland, 2008; Adolphus, Lawton and Dye, 2013). Those who eat breakfast on a daily basis assume optimal development and growth,

there are also positive effects on their alertness, attention, performance on standardized achievement test and other skills important for academic success. (Murphy, Pagano, Nachmani, Sperling, Kane and Kleinman, 1998). Not eating breakfast increases the risk of low blood sugar (Kartashov, Van Horn, Slattery, Jacobs and Ludwig, 2003).

This condition can result to physical symptoms such as, dizziness, weakness, headaches, tingling and a rapid heart rate (Affenito, Thomas Dorazio, Albertson, Leow and Holschuh, 2013). Skipping simply means to leave hurriedly or leave out. It means an act of omission. Therefore breakfast skipping can be defined as an act of omitting breakfast or missing early morning meal or first meal of the day.

Teaching can also be defined as the act of giving lessons on a subject to a class or pupils. It aims at showing the students how to do something. Teaching can be both formal and informal. For example, within a school, teaching takes place as formal education. The aim of teacher is to provide students with new knowledge in various fields, so that they will be equipped with a lot of knowledge. Teaching can be defined as a process of attending to people's needs, experiences and feelings, and making specific interventions to help students learn particular things. (Palmer, 1998). However, teaching is not confined merely to the provision of academic knowledge but also includes; discipline, skills, values and behaviour modification (Adetuyi and Akinola, 2016). Teaching is performed by teachers and takes place throughout a person's life. In most occasions, teaching is a conscious effort. There are different methods used in teaching, some of these include; demonstration method, lecture method and discussion method.

Learning is defined as a gradual change in behaviours of learners which has to be frequently practised and reinforced to prevent its extinction. It is the process by which an individual acquires and retains attitudes, skill, knowledge and capabilities that cannot be attributed to inherited behavioural patterns of physical growth. It can also be defined as the knowledge gained, through experience. This does not necessarily denote acquisition of information but can also be skills, behaviour values, as well. Individuals engage in learning process, till death. Hence it is not confined to school education but captures the experiences of life. It is a must for the growing child. Learning is performed by the student and it is a process that takes place throughout individual's span. It can both be a conscious and an unconscious effort (Adetuyi and Akinola, 2016).

Therefore, teaching-learning process refers to an interactive process, which involves exchange of ideas, values, knowledge and skills between the sender (teacher) and the receiver (learners), which can

formal or informal. The teacher gives instruction and the learner receives and assimilates the instruction which bring about a gradual change in their behaviours.

Breakfast skipping has been observed to be one of the factors, hindering effective teaching-learning process between the teacher and the students. Some students have totally made it a habit to skip early morning meal (breakfast) to avoid being late to school. Some parents prefer giving their children "pocket money" to buy food during break or recess in school, instead of preparing breakfast for them. Some can prepare the food and package it in a flask for the children to eat at school, when opportuned instead of eating it before going to school. This research therefore focused on influence of breakfast skipping on teaching process of Senior Secondary School students in Ondo West Local Government Area, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The major aim of the study was to investigate the influence of breakfast skipping on teaching-learning process of Senior Secondary School (SSS) students in OWLGA of Ondo State. Specifically, the study was carried out to determine:

- i. the occurrence of breakfast skipping among SSS students in OWLGA of Ondo State.
- ii. factors responsible for breakfast skipping of SSS students in OWLGA of Ondo State
- iii. the influence of breakfast skipping on teaching –learning process of SSS students in OWLGA of Ondo State.
- iv. proffered strategies that will help SSS students in OWLGA of Ondo State to overcome the challenge of breakfast skipping.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

1. What is the occurrence of breakfast skipping of SSS students in OWLGA of Ondo State?
2. What are the factors responsible for breakfast skipping of SSS students in OWLGA of Ondo State?
3. Does breakfast skipping influence teaching-learning process of SSS students in OWLGA of Ondo State?
4. What are the strategies that can be used to help SSS students in OWLGA of Ondo State overcome the problems of breakfast skipping?

Method

Design of the Study

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. This is because data generated was generalized on the entire study population.

Population of the Study

The study population was all SSS1 and SSS2 students in OWLGA of Ondo State.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The population size for the study was 4000 SSS1 and 4680 SSS2 students, making the sample for the study to be 8680. Balloting was used to select ten (10) secondary schools from the fifty nine (59) SSS schools in OWLGA of Ondo State. Three percent (3%) of the total number of SSS1 and SSS2 students were used. That is, one hundred and twenty (120) SSS1 students and one hundred and forty (140) SSS2 students were used for the study.

Research Instrument

The research instrument used for this study was self developed structured questionnaire by the researcher which contained twenty five items. The questionnaire was divided into five sections, which were sections A, B, C, D and E. Section A, comprised items on personal data of the students such as class, gender, age and name of the school while sections B,C,D and E comprised, items drawn on the research questions raised for this study. The questionnaire was validated by three experts in human nutrition, two from the Department of Home Economics and one from school of Education all from Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo to ensure that the instrument had both content and face validity.

Data Analysis

The data collected were analysed using frequency distribution and mean (\bar{X}). The mean of the questionnaire items was used and interpreted based on the statistical real limit of the numbers as follows:

<i>Response Category Boundary</i>	<i>Point</i>	<i>Limit</i>
Strongly agree (SA)	4	3.50-4.00
Agree (A)	3	2.50-3.49
Disagree (D)	2	1.50-2.49
Strongly disagree (SD)	1	0.50-1.49

2.50 was the cut-off point accepted as agreed.

Findings

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Class		
SSS1	140	53.85
SSS2	120	46.15
Total	260	100.00
Gender		
Male	162	62.31
Female	98	37.69
Total	260	100.00
Age		
10-14 Years	224	86.15
15-19 Years	36	13.85
Total	260	100.00

Table 2: Occurrence of Breakfast Skipping among SSS Students in OWLGA

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Statements</i>	<i>\bar{X}</i>
1.	I eat breakfast at home before leaving for school.	3.3*
2.	I normally buy and eat breakfast in the school	2.6*
3.	I am selective in the food that I am taking as breakfast.	3.2*
4.	I like eating snacks, early in the morning.	2.8*
5.	I often pack and eat breakfast in school	2.3

* Mean greater or equal to cut-off point (2.5)

Table 2 revealed that, the respondents agreed that they eat breakfast at home before leaving for school, they normally buy and eat breakfast in school, they are selective in the food they take as breakfast, and that they like eating snacks early in the morning.

Table 3: Factors Responsible for Breakfast Skipping among SSS Students in OWLGA

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Statement</i>	<i>\bar{X}</i>
1.	I do not feel hungry in the morning.	2.4
2.	I am dieting.	2.2
3.	I do not have enough time to prepare breakfast.	2.7*
4.	I hate eating breakfast.	3.0*
5.	I rush to school every morning.	2.8*
6.	I do not have time to eat breakfast.	3.2*
7.	Breakfast makes me weak and sleepy.	2.8*
8.	I do not have money for my breakfast.	2.8*

* Mean greater or equal to cut-off point (2.5)

Table 3 revealed that, the respondents agreed that they do not have enough time to prepare breakfast, they hate eating breakfast, they rush to school every morning, they do not have time to eat breakfast, breakfast makes them weak and sleepy, and they do not have money for breakfast.

Table 4: Influence of Breakfast Skipping on Teaching and Learning Process among SSS Students in OWLGA

S/N	Statement	\bar{X}
1.	I can reason very fast without eating breakfast	2.6*
2.	I can write an exam or a test without eating breakfast	2.2
3.	I am always confused during teaching and learning process without breakfast	2.7*
4.	I respond effectively to questions in the course of learning without breakfast	2.4
5.	Taking breakfast enhances my learning ability	3.0*
6.	I am not mentally fit for learning without breakfast	2.5*
7.	Breakfast makes me uncomfortable for learning	2.9*
8.	I am more active and vibrant in class whenever I eat breakfast	3.2*
9.	I can study early in the morning without breakfast	2.3
10.	I do not comprehend without breakfast	3.1*
11.	I perform better whenever I skip breakfast	2.4

* mean greater or equal to cut-off point (2.5)

Table 4 revealed that, the respondents agreed that they can reason very fast without eating breakfast, they are confused during teaching and learning process without breakfast, breakfast enhances their learning ability, they are not mentally fit for learning without breakfast, breakfast make them uncomfortable for learning, they are more active and vibrant in class whenever they take breakfast and they do not comprehend without breakfast.

Table 5: Strategies to help SSS students in OWLGA overcome the problem of breakfast skipping

S/N	Statement	\bar{X}
1.	I occasionally take fruit juice for breakfast.	2.3
2.	My school makes provision for breakfast for all students every morning.	2.4
3.	I sometimes eat leftover food of the previous night.	2.8*
4.	I have cupboard stocked with packaged food.	2.8*
5.	I prefer taking beverages to solid food early in the morning.	3.1*
6.	I occasionally eat fruits early in the morning.	2.9*

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| 7. | If government pays workers salary regularly, my parents will be able to give me money to buy food for breakfast in the school. | 3.2* |
| 8. | If I wake up very early, I will be able to prepare my breakfast before going to school. | 2.8* |
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Table 5 revealed that, the respondents agreed that they sometimes eat leftover food of the previous night, they have cupboard stocked with packaged food, they prefer taking beverages to solid food early in the morning, they occasionally eat fruits early in the morning, if government pays workers salary regularly their parents will be able to give them money to buy food for breakfast in the school, and if they wake up very early, they will be able to prepare their breakfast before going to school.

Discussion

Findings of this study revealed that, there is an occurrence of breakfast skipping among Senior Secondary Schools students in OWLGA of Ondo State. Some students do not eat breakfast before leaving home, some buy and eat breakfast at school, some pack breakfast from home and eat it at school and some are selective in the food they take, as breakfast. Acham, Kikafunda, Malde, Oldewage-Theron and Egal (2012) findings and submissions that breakfast skipping is becoming prominent among Senior Secondary School students and may lead to micronutrient deficiency and poor nutritional status.

This study also discovered that the following factors are responsible for breakfast skipping among SSS students in OWLGA of Ondo State; inadequate time to prepare breakfast, waking up late in the morning, breakfast make some weak and sleepy, lack of money to buy food for breakfast and dieting. The findings was buttressed by Kral, Heo, Whiteford and Faith (2012) that breakfast skipping is based on some factors such as not having time to cook, feeling sleepy after taking breakfast, rising up late from bed and poverty. Results of this study showed some influences of breakfast skipping on teaching and learning process of SSS students in OWLGA of Ondo State. These include: being confused during teaching and learning without breakfast; inability to respond to questions effectively; mental unfitness; being uncomfortable while attempting to learn and being unable to study and comprehend. These results were in line with Wesnes, Pincock and Scholey (2012) views that, eating breakfast has a positive effect on children's cognitive performance, particularly in the domain of memory.

Abdullah (2006) discovered that eating breakfast has been linked extensively to better performance of students in the classroom. Eating

breakfast also help to control appetite and keep the students focused on learning throughout the day. Eating a healthy breakfast in the morning has beneficial effects on the memory and attention span by allowing students to quickly and accurately retrieve information. He stated further that, students who eat breakfast perform better in arithmetic and problem-solving tests.

Findings of the study also revealed that the following strategies can be used to help them overcome the problem of breakfast skipping, eating fruits early in the morning, taking beverages instead of solid foods early in the morning, having their cupboard stocked with packaged food, taking fruits juice as breakfast, prompt payment of workers salary by the government to make the parents buoyant enough to provide food for their children, eating leftovers which will sustain and keep the individual active for some hours before solid meal is eaten later in the day and this will make the students vibrant and attentive in the class. Frank (2009) also opined that, children who often avoid breakfast should take beverages, eat fruits and enough water in the morning which will sustain them for 3 to 5 hours before a balanced meal is eaten during the day and also prevent stomach disorder.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that, SSS students in OWLGA of Ondo State skip breakfast and that there are various factors responsible for it. Skipping breakfast could also influence teaching and learning process of students in the aspects of reasoning, comprehension and comfort among others. There are also various strategies that could be used to help students to overcome the problem of breakfast skipping. These include; abundant provision of food by parents to their children, encouraging students to eat breakfast before going to school and encouraging them to develop the habit of waking up early to prepare breakfast.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Parents should make provision for their children abundantly.
- ii. Students should be encouraged to often take their breakfast before going to school.
- iii. Government should pay workers' salaries regularly (workers are mostly the parents of these students) to make them buoyant enough to provide breakfast for their children.

- iv. The students should be encouraged to develop the habit of waking up early to prepare their breakfasts.
- v. Students' cupboards should be well stocked with fast food and can meal which they can grab and take to school as breakfast.
- vi. Snacks, fruits or fruit juice can be eaten as breakfast, when students do not feel like cooking or preparing any meal. This will sustain and keep them active for some hours before they would eat solid meal later in the day.

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